

Effect of the structural changes, correlation and role of donor atoms on the stabilities of some binary lanthanone(III) heterochelates in aqueous media

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The present paper describes a potentiometric study on formation constant of binary complexes of lanthanone with oxy, thio, amino acids, amines and phenols at constant temperature $25 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$ and ionic strength $\mu = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (NaClO_4). Various factors influencing the formation and stability of binary complexes have been discussed.

In continuation of our earlier work¹ in the present investigation an attempt has been made to study and effect of structural changes, their correlation and role of donor atoms, on formation constants of binary heterochelates of lanthanone(III) ions.

Results and discussion

The potentiometric titrations of perchloric acid, perchlo-

ric acid + ligand and perchloric acid-ligand + metal were carried out against carbon dioxide free standard sodium hydroxide using Irving-Rossotti method. The proton ligand and metal ligand formation constants of the ligands and trivalent lanthanone(III) ions with oxy, thio, amino acids, amines and phenols were calculated. The data of proton ligand and metal-ligand formation constants are presented in Table 1. The order of the formation constants for the

Table 1. Proton-ligand and binary metal-ligand formation constants of the complexes

Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ\text{C}$, (ionic strength) $\mu = 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-1}$ (NaClO_4)

Ligand	pk_1^{H}	pk_2^{H}	pk_3^{H}	La^{III}		Ce^{III}		Pr^{III}		Nd^{III}		Sm^{III}		Gd^{III}	
				$\log k_1$	$\log k_2$										
Glycolic acid	10.74	3.47	–	5.54	4.72	5.83	4.85	5.80	4.76	5.35	5.49	6.08	5.63	6.18	5.29
Lactic acid	11.12	3.57	–	6.47	4.64	6.32	5.67	6.32	5.54	6.75	5.87	6.63	5.90	6.54	5.93
Malic acid	11.58	4.81	3.19	4.51	4.30	5.23	4.75	5.04	4.52	5.66	5.36	5.42	4.58	6.33	5.39
Thio glycolic acid	10.39	3.39	–	6.00	5.21	5.96	5.16	6.08	5.33	5.87	4.81	6.04	5.47	6.17	5.90
Thio lactic acid	10.40	3.44	–	5.57	5.17	5.99	5.24	6.24	5.64	6.36	5.62	6.69	5.75	6.67	6.09
Thio malic acid	10.54	4.40	2.96	6.13	5.41	6.29	5.41	6.07	5.90	6.51	4.82	6.24	5.76	6.32	5.54
Glycine	9.60	2.31	–	4.09	3.49	4.42	3.52	4.40	3.74	4.50	4.12	5.14	4.34	4.64	4.53
α -Alanine	9.76	2.31	–	3.76	3.43	4.29	3.49	4.57	4.00	4.80	3.60	5.10	4.09	5.18	4.23
Aspartic acid	9.60	3.60	–	5.30	5.01	5.72	5.44	5.48	5.00	5.02	4.87	5.89	4.92	5.65	5.22
Catechol	11.30	9.34	–	8.30	–	9.18	–	9.48	–	9.84	–	9.58	–	10.08	–
Pyrogallol	10.77	8.94	–	8.85	–	9.75	–	9.75	–	10.42	–	10.15	–	10.05	–
Protocatechuic acid	2.25	8.97	4.43	9.28	–	10.08	–	10.18	–	11.41	–	10.48	–	10.68	–
Ethylenediamine	9.77	7.04	–	3.70	3.12	3.67	3.45	4.26	2.90	3.98	3.39	4.44	3.54	4.22	3.84
1,2-Diamino propane	9.85	6.97	–	3.75	1.93	4.35	2.97	4.53	3.12	4.42	3.25	4.68	3.67	4.44	4.10
1,3-Diamino propane	9.56	8.19	–	3.02	2.34	3.23	2.36	3.53	2.76	3.61	2.44	4.22	3.69	4.59	3.51
<i>N,N'</i> -Diethyl-ethylenediamine	9.89	6.73	–	5.02	3.42	5.20	3.86	4.99	3.92	5.03	3.82	5.05	3.84	5.68	4.54
<i>N,N'</i> -Dimethyl-ethylenediamine	10.50	7.09	–	4.21	2.71	4.49	3.30	4.38	3.10	4.09	3.69	4.33	3.54	4.68	4.21

Minimum deviation = ± 0.05 unit.

binary oxy, thio, amino acid, amines, and phenol systems are as follows : glycolic acid < lactic acid > malic acid, thio glycolic acid \approx thiolactic acid < thiomalic acid, glycine \approx α -alanine < aspartic acid. *N,N'*-diethyl ethylenediamine > *N,N'*-dimethyl ethylenediamine > 1,2-diamino propane and protocatechuic acid < catechol < pyrogallol.

The order² of the coordinating tendencies of the above five series is as follows : phenols > oxy acids > thio acids > amines > amino acids. In addition to the formation constants and coordinating tendencies of the above five series. The stabilities of the trivalent lanthanone with glycolic acid, thio glycolic acid, glycine, ethylenediamine and catachol follows the order : La < Ce \approx Pr < Nd > Sm < Gd; La \approx Ce < Pr > Nd < Sm < Gd; La < Ce \approx Pr < Nd < Sm > Gd; La \approx Ce < Nd < Pr \approx Gd < Sm and La < Ce < Pr < Nd > Sm < Gd respectively. The above formation constant orders of all the ligands and series have been explained in the terms of their structures and basicities³. Besides this, the size of the metal ion and ionic potential are two important factors in deciding the value of formation constant.

The proton-ligand formation constant of phenols are higher compared to amino acids hence it is obvious that phenols form more stable complexes. The presence of resonance effect of phenol, ring delocalized π orbitals also play an important role in binding of the ligand. Thus, M-O bond becomes more stronger in phenols. From the proton-ligand stability constant values of oxy acids, it is expected that their formation constants should be higher than the corresponding thio acids with lanthanones. But the formation constant values of oxy and thioacids are nearly the same.

The charge transfer into continuum orbitals of sulphur is responsible for higher values of formation constants of thio acids. The proton-ligand constant of malic acid is higher than that of glycolic acid and lactic acid. It acts as tridentate ligand. It forms less stable complexes than glycolic and lactic acids. This is due to bigger size of malic acid molecule, creating steric hindrance, which alters the stability of malic acid complexes. Thio glycolic acid and thio lactic acid are bidentate while TMA is tridentate ligand coordination being from -SH and two -COOH groups.

The calculated metal-ligand formation constant values are in agreement with the proton ligand formation constants of the amino acids. The interaction of amino acids anion with lanthanone(III) ion is comparatively less than the corresponding oxy and thio acids. This results in lowering of the formation constant values of the amino acids.

The metal-ligand formation constant values are in agreement with the proton ligand formation constants of the

amines. The basicity of the ethylenediamine and glycine is nearly same. Hence their tendencies to form complexes should be the same 1,3-diamino propane forms six membered chelate ring while all other amines forms a five membered ring in coordination with lanthanone(III) ions. So complexes of 1,3-diamino propane are least stable; lower pK_1^H value of the 1,3-diamino propane indicates least basicity in these group of amines. The proton-ligand formation constant values, confirms the above order. The basic strength of ligand *N,N*-diethyl ethylenediamine is higher than *N,N*-dimethyl ethylenediamine, but steric hindrance of two -C₂H₅ groups on two chelating nitrogen atoms have lowered the strength of M-*N,N*-diethyl ethylenediamine than M-*N,N*-dimethyl ethylenediamine. The proton ligand formation constant for ethylenediamine and 1,2-diamino propane are nearly same. In some cases there is deviation in the order of metal-ligand formation constants. This may be due to the combined effect of ligand basicity, size of the metal ion and charge/ratio also plays an important role in the value of binary formation constant⁴. This may be due to the effect of steric hindrance due to -C₂H₅ group or -CH₃ group present in such ligands.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of A.R. grade. The metal nitrate solutions of desired concentrations were prepared from their respective higher molar stock solutions. Free perchloric acid, sodium hydroxide and metal nitrates were standardized by acid base⁵ and complexometric⁶ methods. The proton-ligand and binary metal-ligand formation constants were determined in aqueous media $\mu = 0.2$ mol dm⁻³ (NaClO₄) and 25 \pm 0.1°C using Irving-Rossotti⁷ titration technique. The 1 : 10 ratio of M : L was used for the equilibrium study. Nitrogen gas was used to create inert atmosphere. The pH measurements were carried out with a controlled dynamics pH meter fitted with a combination of glass-calomel electrode assembly.

The values of proton ligand stability constant pK_1^H , pK_2^H and pK_3^H and metal ligand formation constants of binary mono (1 : 1) and bis (1 : 2) M(III) L complexes were calculated from the potentiometric data using Rossotti-Rossotti technique⁷. The least square⁷ method was used to get the precise values of formation constants.

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Note

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